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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The World Development Indicators (WDI) database is the World Bank's flagship collection of cross-country comparable development statistics. It provides nearly 1,600 indicators covering economic, social, demographic, and environmental dimensions for around 220 economies and 45 country groups, with time series extending back more than five decades. Data are sourced from national and international organisations and institutions, ensuring broad coverage but also leading to methodological variation. The WDI is freely accessible via the World Bank's Open Data platform, DataBank, bulk downloads, and an Application Programming Interface (API). While it is a vital tool for research, policy, and monitoring progress on global goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), data availability across countries and years remains uneven, particularly for social policy indicators. As shown by coverage in Discuss Data relevant countries, core demographic and economic series are well established, whereas indicators on poverty, health, and education are often fragmented or incomplete. Despite these limitations, the WDI remains the most comprehensive statistical resource of the World Bank and a cornerstone for global comparative research.

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Data Review – World Development Indicators (WDI)

The World Development Indicators (WDI) database is the World Bank’s “comprehensive collection of global development data, providing key economic, social, and environmental statistics” (9). It is considered the World Bank’s premier statistical product and serves as a central resource for policymakers, researchers, and analysts worldwide (7; 9). The database currently (as of September 2025) contains about “1,600 time-series indicators for almost 220 economies and more than 45 country groups” (5), with coverage often going back more than five decades (5). Its overarching goal is to offer cross-country comparable, reliable, and accessible data that can be used to inform research, policymaking, and public debate on development challenges (9; 7).

Key Features

The WDI includes information on economic, social, and environmental dimensions of development, among others ranging from poverty and inequality to trade, infrastructure, and governance (8). Data is collected from official national and international sources to ensure high-quality information across countries (7; 9).

The indicators can be accessed through multiple platforms: the World Bank’s Open Data site as well as the interactive DataBank tool and allows downloads of Excel or CSV files (7). In addition, the WDI enables users to customise their data queries by selecting specific databases, countries, indicators, and time periods – as well as download their selected outcomes (11).

Beyond data access, the WDI also functions as a reference point for monitoring global development goals, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), by providing standardised and timely statistics (9). In 2018, the World Bank introduced the WDI website as “a new discovery tool and storytelling platform” (6), designed to enhance accessibility and highlight methodological aspect of the data (6).

Indicators

The WDI includes around 1,600 indicators, organised by key themes such as poverty and inequality, people, environment, economy, states and markets, and global links (11; 7). These indicators encompass a wide spectrum, from macroeconomic aggregates like the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth to social measures such as maternal mortality, school enrolment, and gender representation in parliament (11; Appendix - Table 1). Information on definitions, coverage, and sources is available through the Metadata Glossary, ensuring transparency about how indicators are compiled and maintained (10).

The indicators are drawn from officially recognised international organisations, such as the United Nations, the World Health Organization (WHO), the International Labour

Organization (ILO), UNESCO, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), and others, depending on the topic (11; Appendix - Table 1).

Discuss Data Country Coverage

The WDI aims to provide global coverage, but data availability for specific indicators and countries is uneven (Appendix - Table 1).

Table 1 in the Appendix illustrates the coverage for some randomly selected indicators for the countries relevant to Discuss Data, including Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz Republic, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan. For example – as of September 2025 – data on *life expectancy at birth (female)* is consistently available across all reviewed countries since 1960 up until 2023 (exception Kyrgyz Republic: data only available up to 2022), while *multidimensional poverty ratios* are often limited to single years or entirely missing (11; Appendix - Table 1).

The health-related indicator of *maternal mortality ratio* is partially covered from 1985, with time gaps in countries like Georgia and Tajikistan (11; Appendix - Table 1). The education-related variables of *children out of school* or *progression to secondary school* are available but fragmented, with gaps across years (11; Appendix - Table 1). Data on the *coverage of social insurance programs* exist but is not – or only for a few years – available for several countries (11; Appendix - Table 1).

This variation highlights both the strength and limitations of the WDI as a source for cross-country comparisons: while core demographic and economic indicators are covered, more specialised social policy measures may be incomplete or sporadic (11; Appendix - Table 1).

On a critical note - while the WDI aggregates around 1,600 indicators, coverage across countries and years is highly uneven (11). As the examples in Table 1 demonstrate, even for basic development measures such as maternal mortality or school progression, data availability varies substantially between countries, with some series stopping in the 2010s or consisting of only scattered observations (11). This patchiness undermines the comparability of time series and restricts the ability to conduct consistent longitudinal analyses across all Discuss Data relevant countries (11). As for the number of indicators: one WDI website mentions ~1,400 indicators (8), one ~1,500 (9), and one ~1,600 (5). However, the WDI DataBank itself lists 1,516 indicators (as of September 2025) (11).

Framework and Data Collection

The WDI compiles data from a broad range of primary providers, including national statistical offices, international organisations, and specialised UN agencies (7; 11). This multi-source approach ensures comprehensive coverage but also explains inconsistencies, as methodologies and data collection practices may vary between institutions (7).

By integrating such diverse sources, the WDI facilitates both macro-level analysis of global trends and micro-level studies of specific indicators (9).

Access

The WDI is freely accessible (7). Users can download data, interact with it through visualisation tools, or query it via the Application Programming Interface (API) (5; 3). Archived versions of the database dating back to 1989 are also available, allowing for historical comparisons and reproducibility of past analyses (5).

World Bank Databases

While the World Bank maintains a wide portfolio of specialised databases tailored to a particular thematic or regional focus (7; 11), the World Development Indicators stand out as very comprehensive and widely used.

For instance, while the Global Economic Monitor (GEM) offers “updates of high-frequency indicators on global economic developments, encompassing both advanced economies and emerging market and developing economies” (12), other datasets, such as the Enterprise Surveys or the Doing Business database, concentrate on private sector dynamics and regulatory environments (1; 4). Whereas thematic platforms like the Gender Data Portal or the World Integrated Trade Solution (WITS) address specific domains of policy analysis (2; 8). Compared to these more narrowly scoped resources, the WDI functions as the flagship database, integrating economic, social, demographic, and environmental indicators into a single database (7).

Note

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Sources

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Appendix

Table 1: Example Indicator Coverage of Discuss Data Relevant Countries (as of September 2025)

Country	Indicator	Years Covered (max. 1960-2024)
Armenia	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2015
	Income share held by lowest 20%	2001-2023
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2017
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	2002 & 2003, 2005-2007, 2011-2023
	Progression to secondary school (%)	2002-2007, 2011, 2013-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	2019-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2008-2022
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	2004-2015
Azerbaijan	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	No data
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1995, 2001-2005
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2017
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	2000-2023
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1998-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	2008-2010, 2020 & 2021
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024

	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-1999, 2001-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	Data only available for 2015
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1996-1999, 2008-2022
Belarus	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	No data
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1993, 1995, 1998-2020
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2003, 2007-2014
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	1995, 2001-2023
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1971-1985, 1991-1996, 1998-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	1992-2002, 2005-2019
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	2001-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2008-2010, 2012-2019
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1992-2023
Estonia	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	No data
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1993, 1995, 1998, 2000-2022
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2016
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1993-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	1995 & 1996, 1998-2000, 2014-2022
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1995, 1998-2001,

		2003 & 2004, 2007-2016
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	1998-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	No data
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1991-2023
Georgia	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2018
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1996-2023
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-1992, 1994-2001, 2004 & 2005, 2007, 2009, 2013 & 2014, 2016-2018,
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	1995-1197, 2004-2009, 2011-2023
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1995 & 1996, 1999-2002, 2004-2009, 2011-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	1995-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997 & 1998, 2000-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	No data
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1995-2007
Kazakhstan	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2015
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1993, 1996. 2001-2021
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023

	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2015
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	2000-2023
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1996, 2000-2018
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	2010-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2007, 2010, 2014 & 2015, 2017-2021
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1997-1999, 2010-2018
Kyrgyz Republic	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2018
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1998, 2000-2022
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2022
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2016
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	1996, 1999-2022
	Progression to secondary school (%)	2000-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	2014-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2006, 2011-2020
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	2014-2023
Latvia	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	No data
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1993, 1995-1998, 2002-2022
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023

	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2015
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	1999, 2008-2022
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1995 & 1996, 1999-2005, 2007-2016
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	Data only available for 1994
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2008 & 2009
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1994-2023
Lithuania	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	No data
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1993, 1996, 1998-2022
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2017
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2023
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	1998-2003, 2013-2022
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1995 & 1996, 1998-2016
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	1998-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	Data only available for 2008
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1991, 1993-2023

Moldova	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2012
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1997-2019, 2021 & 2022
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2005, 2009-2016
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	2014-2020
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1994, 1999-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	1995-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997, 1999-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2010, 2012 & 2013, 2017 & 2018
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1996-2023
	Russia	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1993, 1996-2021
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2015
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	1994 & 1995, 2006-2009, 2011-2023
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1999 & 2000, 2007 & 2008, 2011-2015,
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	1998-2002, 2005-2023
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997 & 1998, 2000-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023

	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2007, 2014-2017
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1999-2023
Tajikistan	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2017
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1999, 2003 & 2004, 2007, 2009, 2015
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2005, 2016
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	2000-2017
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1998-2011, 2013-2016
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	2000 & 2001
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	Data only available for 2011
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1998-2001, 2003 & 2004, 2021-2023
Turkmenistan	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2019
	Income share held by lowest 20%	Data only available for 1998
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2015
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	No data
	Progression to secondary school (%)	No data
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	No data
Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024	

	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997 & 1998, 2000-2003, 2005-2007, 2009-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	No data
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	No data
Ukraine	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2012
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1992 & 1993, 1995 & 1996, 1999, 2002-2020
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023
	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2012, 2014 & 2015
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2021
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	2002-2021
	Progression to secondary school (%)	1971-1973, 1976-1979, 1981-1984, 1990-1993, 1998 & 1999, 2001, 2005-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	1999 & 2000, 2008-2020
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2021
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997, 1999-2001, 2003-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	2006, 2011-2013, 2015-2020
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	1999-2023
Uzbekistan	Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Data only available for 2021
	Income share held by lowest 20%	1998, 2000, 2002 & 2003, 2021-2023
	Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	1960-2023

	Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	1985-2005, 2009-2016
	Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	2000-2022
	Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	1992-2023
	Children out of school (% of primary school age)	2007-2023
	Progression to secondary school (%)	2000-2017
	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	No data
	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	1990-2024
	Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	1997 & 1998, 2000-2024
	Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	1960-2023
	Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	Data only available for 2018
	Social contributions (% of revenue)	2011-2023

Sources used for indicators	
Multidimensional poverty headcount ratio (UNDP) (% of population)	Alkire, S., Kanagaratnam, U., and Suppa, N. (2023). 'The global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) 2023 country results and methodological note', OPHI
Income share held by lowest 20%	World Bank, Poverty and Inequality Platform (primary household survey data obtained from government statistical agencies and World Bank country departments)
Life expectancy at birth, female (year)	World Population Prospects, United Nations (UN); national statistical offices; Eurostat (ESTAT)
Maternal mortality ratio (national estimate, per 100,000 live births)	Maternal Mortality Estimation Inter-Agency Group (MMEIG), World Health Organization (WHO)
Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$)	Global Health Expenditure database, World Health Organization (WHO)
Immunization, measles (% of children ages 12-23 months)	World Health Organization (WHO)
Children out of school (% of primary school age)	Stat Bulk Data Download Service, UN Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)
Progression to secondary school (%)	Stat Bulk Data Download Service, UN Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)

Central government debt, total (% of GP)	Government Finance Statistics Yearbook and data files, International Monetary Fund (IMF)
Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%) (modeled ILO estimate)	ILO Modelled Estimates database (ILOEST), International Labour Organization (ILO)
Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments (%)	Monthly ranking of women in national parliaments, Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU)
Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 women ages 15-19)	World Population Prospects, United Nations (UN), publisher: UN Population Division
Coverage of social insurance programs (% of population)	ASPIRE: The Atlas of Social Protection - Indicators of Resilience and Equity, World Bank (WB)
Social contributions (% of revenue)	Government Finance Statistics Yearbook and data files, International Monetary Fund (IMF)

(source: 11)